

HYDRATION OF ALUMINIUM OXIDE SOLS

BY A. K. M. TRIVEDI, K. M. BUCH AND M. J. PATANI

Hydration of micelles in the case of aluminium oxide sols may be obtained by studying the distribution of ammonium ion across a semipermeable membrane. After allowing for the membrane-equilibrium effect, calculated indirectly, it has been found that 25.2 moles of water per mole of aluminium oxide are present in the micelles. An alternative method of obtaining hydration is to determine viscosity at low concentration, calculate hydration according to Einstein's equation and to extrapolate the hydration values so obtained to zero concentration of aluminium oxide. Both the methods provide results of the same order.

The properties of metallic oxide sols are governed by both the charge as well as the solvation of the micelles (Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1926, pp. 521, 625). Such sols are on the border line between hydrophobic and hydrophilic sols. Although aluminium oxide sols are known to be hydrated (Weiser, "Inorganic Colloid Chemistry", Vol. II, 1935, p. 117), it appears that no attempt has been made to measure quantitatively the extent of hydration directly.

One method (Trivedi and Divatia, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 37A, 33) whereby the hydration of the micelles may be obtained is to consider the distribution of an electrolyte like ammonium chloride across a semipermeable membrane. The distribution of ammonium ions across a membrane is affected by (i) the adsorption of ammonium ions by the micelles, (ii) Donnan-membrane equilibrium and (iii) hydration of micelles. The first is improbable and may be ruled out. Hence, the distribution of ammonium ion will be affected by (ii) and (iii). The hydration of the micelles may be obtained provided that one can calculate the membrane-equilibrium effect.

An alternative method of determining hydration is the measurement of viscosity of the sol. Thus, Hatschek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1912, 11, 280) concluded that the increase in viscosity with dispersion as observed by Óden (*Der Kolloide Schwefel*", Upsala, 1913, p. 89) in the case of Rafo sulphur sol could be explained by assuming that micelles in the case of sulphur sol were hydrated. For hydrophilic sols Kruyt also observed: "The decrease of $(n_s - n_0)/n_0$ from the point of view of Einstein's equation must be interpreted as the process of desolvation" ("Colloid Science", Part II, 1949, p. 201). The interpretation of viscosity data is, however, beset with considerable difficulties (Freundlich, *loc. cit.*, p. 539).

EXPERIMENTAL

Methods of preparation and analysis of the sols have been reported earlier (Trivedi and Buch, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 337). To determine NH_4^+ ion, an aliquot portion of the sol was coagulated, filtered and washed and the filtrate was treated with an excess of standard NaOH solution. The solution was boiled till free of ammonia, cooled, excess of standard HCl added and the excess was titrated against NaOH (Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1948, p. 305). The following sols were used for various experiments.

TABLE I

Sol.	Al ₂ O ₃ Chloride. (in g./litre)	Method.	Hydration (in moles of water per mole of Al ₂ O ₃).
A	30.12 1.418	Membrane equilibrium	25.2
B	19.24 0.460	Viscosity	26.0
C	15.50 0.212	„	38.0

Membrane Equilibrium.—A partially dialysed sol, admixed with ammonium chloride (far below the C. V.), was kept in collodion bags, suspended in water. After attainment of equilibrium the sol inside (I) and very dilute sol outside (E) the bag were analysed for different constituents. The results of the membrane equilibrium experiments are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Expt.	Concentration of Al ₂ O ₃ (g./litre).			Conc. of NH ₄ ⁺ (m.e./litre).		Apparent density.	S.H.V.
	I.	E.	(I-E).	*X.	F.		
1	26.20	0.120	26.08	54.7	59.6	0.2542	15.7
2	24.92	0.560	24.36	52.1	58.3	0.2276	17.6
3	26.22	0.760	25.46	52.4	63.2	0.1964	20.4
4	26.48	0.400	26.08	53.5	61.6	0.1981	20.2
5	26.20	0.140	26.06	58.8	67.3	0.2070	19.3
6	25.86	0.130	25.73	58.2	66.8	0.2057	19.5

* Calculated as shown below.

Mean 18.8

Viscosity.—The viscosity of the sols at different dilutions was determined by Ostwald viscometers at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

DISCUSSION

The aluminium oxide sol was stabilised by aluminium chloride and contained free ammonium chloride added as a reference substance. To calculate hydration effect, it is necessary to estimate the membrane equilibrium effect which, however, cannot be obtained directly. It may be indirectly calculated assuming that 20% of the adsorbed Al³⁺ ions are effective in the membrane equilibrium.

The concentration of adsorbed Al³⁺ ions will be equal to the concentration of the chloride, the counter-ion. Knowing the concentration of chloride-ion per g. of aluminium oxide in the original sol, the concentration of adsorbed ion responsible for the membrane equilibrium can be calculated. An example will make the procedure clear.

The original sol contains 30.12 g./litre of Al₂O₃ and 1.418 g./litre (0.040 g.e./litre) of chloride. Hence, the adsorbed chloride per g. of Al₂O₃ will be $0.040/30.12 = 0.0013$ g.e. of chloride per g. of colloid. In the experiment 1 (Table I) the difference in concentrations of aluminium oxide, inside and outside the membrane, is 26.08 g./litre. Hence, the concentration of adsorbed chloride is $0.0013 \times 26.08 = 0.0339$ g.e./litre, i.e. 33.9 m.e./litre. Assuming that 20% of the adsorbed ions are active in membrane equilibrium, the effective concentration of the adsorbed ions will be $33.9/5$ m.e./litre.

Hence, following Donnan's fundamental relation (Bolam, "The Donnan Equilibria", 1932, p. 4) it can be easily shown that

$$X^2 = (NH_4)_1 \times \left[(NH_4)_1 + \frac{Al^{3+}}{5} \right]$$

where 'X' is the hypothetical concentration of NH_4^+ ion outside the membrane, assuming that the membrane equilibrium effect alone is effective, and $(NH_4)_1$ is the measured concentration of ammonium ions inside the membrane (data not given);

$$\therefore X^2 = 51.4 \times (51.4 + 6.77); X = 54.7 \text{ m.e./litre.}$$

In all cases 'X' was found to be less than the concentration of NH_4^+ ion outside the membrane. This difference is due to hydration of the micelles, *i.e.*, a part of the solvent is immobilised in the colloidal particle. Knowing the value of X, the apparent density, *D*, and specific hydrodynamic volume S.H.V. can be calculated by a procedure similar to the one previously employed (Trivedi and Divatia, *loc. cit.*). Taking the average value of S.H.V. as 18.8 and density of Al_2O_3 as 4.0 g./c.c. (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. V, 1946, p. 265) there will be 17.8 g. of water to 4.0 g. of aluminium oxide or $(17.8/1) \times (102/4) = 25.2$ moles of water per mole of aluminium oxide (M.W. of $Al_2O_3 = 102$).

In membrane equilibrium experiments, apart from the inherent experimental errors involved, selecting 20% of total adsorbed ions as responsible for membrane equilibrium effect is somewhat arbitrary. In the conductivity experiments (Trivedi and Buch, *loc. cit.*) about 0.3 part of the total adsorbed ions is considered free. But the sols used for membrane equilibrium were of lower purity and were likely to contain free $AlCl_3$. The actual concentration of fixed Al^{3+} ion may be somewhat lower and, hence, taking 20% of the total analytically determined ions as responsible for the membrane equilibrium appears to be justified. If 30% of the ions are considered responsible for the membrane equilibrium effect, the hydration value obtained will be about 25% lower. Even the experimental variation in S.H.V. is about 15%. Besides, the value of hydration increases both with purity and concentration. An alternative method of determining hydration in the case of these sols is by determination of viscosity. Knowing the specific viscosity $(\eta_s/\eta_0 - 1)$ of the sol and determining the density of the sol as well as of water, it is possible to calculate hydration of micelles at any particular concentration.

In the case of diluted sol B, when the concentration is 3.100 g./litre of Al_2O_3 , the relative viscosity is 1.29. If *f* is the volume of suspended particles (Weiser, "Inorganic Colloid Chemistry", Vol. III, 1938, p. 178),

$$f = \frac{\eta/\eta_0 - 1}{k} \text{ where } k \text{ is taken as } 2.5 \text{ and } \eta/\eta_0 = 1.29.$$

$$\therefore f = \frac{1.29 - 1}{2.5} = 0.116.$$

Knowing the density of the sol (d_s) and that of water (d_w), the apparent density (d) of the micelles can be easily obtained (Weiser, *loc. cit.*).

$$d = \frac{d_s - d_w}{f} + d_w$$

$$\therefore d = \frac{1.0018 - 0.9941}{0.116} + 0.9941 = \frac{0.0077}{0.116} + 0.9941 = 1.06002$$

Assuming 'x' to be the volume fraction of water, (1-x) will be the volume fraction of Al_2O_3 particles. If the density of Al_2O_3 is taken as 4.0 g./c.c. (Mellor, *loc. cit.*), it follows that $0.9941x + 4.0(1-x) = 1.06002$.

Solving the above equation, $x = 0.97804$ and $(1-x) = 0.02196$. The molecular weight of Al_2O_3 is 102 and that of water is 18; therefore,

$$\text{Hydration} = \frac{0.9941 \times 0.97804}{18} \times \frac{102}{4.0 \times 0.02196} = 62.3 \text{ moles of water per mole of } \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3.$$

FIG. 1

The hydration value obtained as above in the case of both the sol may be plotted against concentration. The value of "apparent" hydration increases rapidly with concentration. However, by plotting the values of hydration for lower concentrations and extrapolating them to zero concentration, one may obtain 'real' hydration value. The values come out to be 38 and 26 moles of water per mole of aluminium oxide (see Fig. 1). The rapid increase in viscosity and the 'apparent' values of hydration are due to the non-Newtonian behaviour of the sol at finite concentration. However, extrapolation procedure, as shown above, does yield results which are of the same order as in the membrane equilibrium experiments (see Table I).

From this one may conclude that the viscosity method applied as above is of some use in indicating the order of hydration of micelles in such systems.

Thanks of the authors are due to the Ahmedabad Education Society for a generous grant towards chemicals and apparatus.